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Abstract: Migration governance entails a global regime based on the coordination and management of migrations, employing the discourse of human rights to guide “orderly migration”, which, in practice, causes a security effect. This occurs through vertically institutionalized political and legal processes that consider migration as a threat to national security, and justify the use of extraordinary control and restriction measures. This chapter explains how migration governance influences the management of migration processes in Latin America (LA). I analyze the negative impact of this hegemonic securitization discourse on the “fight” against human trafficking (HT) in LA, coordinated by the Organization of American States (OAS). The initial hypothesis is that the action against HT developed by the OAS prioritizes the securitization approach over a humanitarian one.

Keywords: Migration management, securitization, human trafficking, Latin America, OAS.

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